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Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(v) with *N*-Hydroxy-*N,N'*-diarylbenzamide in Presence of *p*-Hydroxybenzaldehyde†

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N-Hydroxy-*N,N'*-diarylbenzamides have been found to be potential analytical reagents for determination of various transition elements¹. The present paper reports the use of a newly synthesised reagent *N*-hydroxy-*N-p*-chlorophenyl-*N'*-(2,3-dimethyl)phenyl-*p*-toluamide hydrochloride for the extractive photometric determination of vanadium(v). The proposed method based on the chloroform-extraction of vanadium as V-HCPDMPTH-*p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde complex and its subsequent photometric determination is rapid and better in sensitivity and selectivity than the other established methods².

Experimental

Uv spectra were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss GS-865 Specord spectrophotometer equipped with 1-cm matched silica cuvettes for all photometric measurements.

A stock solution of vanadium(v) was prepared by dissolving ammonium metavanadate (A.R.) in double-distilled water, and its vanadium was evaluated volumetrically using potassium permanganate solution³.

N-Hydroxy-*N-p*-chlorophenyl-*N'*-(2,3-dimethyl)phenyl-*p*-toluamide hydrochloride was synthesised by coupling an equimolar mixture of *N*-(2,3-dimethyl)phenyl-*p*-toluimidoyl chloride and *N-p*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine in ether medium at 5°. The resulting hydrochloride was crystallised from absolute ethanol containing few drops of HCl (A.R.). C, H, and N values of the compound

were found satisfactory. A 0.003 *M* solution of HCPDMPTH and 0.2 *M* solutions of the *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde were prepared in chloroform and used in extraction.

Procedure: An aliquot of vanadium(v) solution containing 100 µg of V was transferred to a separatory funnel, diluted to 25 ml with distilled water and adjusted the pH 1.5–5.2 with 2 *M* HCl and dilute ammonia. A 0.003 *M* reagent solution (15 ml) and 0.2 *M* *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde solution (5 ml) were then added. After shaking the funnel for 2 min, the chloroform layer separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The aqueous phase was then washed with chloroform (2×4 ml). The coloured extracts were transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask and the volume made up with chloroform. The absorbance was then measured at 590 nm against chloroform as a blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra: The absorption spectra of vanadium(v)–HCPDMPTH complex in the absence and presence of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde were scanned. The vanadium–HCPDMPTH complex shows a flat peak at 570–590 nm with molar absorptivity of about 900 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. In the presence of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, a 1:2:1 (metal–HCPDMPTH–*p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde) bluish green mixed-complex is formed with molar absorptivity of 7 900 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Effect of variables: Various non-polar organic solvents were tried and chloroform was found to be most satisfactory because it gives high distribution ratios for the reagent and mixed complexes. The optimum pH range was found to be 1.5–5.2. A 4-fold molar excess of reagent and at least 250-fold molar excess of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde was necessary for the complete extraction of vanadium. The order of addition of reagents was not critical. Sodium, potassium and ammonium sulphates and chlorides were tried as salting out agents in the concentration range 0.5–3.0 *M* but did not enhance the extraction. The extracts were stable for at least 40 h at 27±2°.

Characteristics of complexes: The system obeyed Beer's law in the range 0.8–6.4 ppm of V. The optimum concentration range on the basis of Ringbom plots was found to be 1.2–5.8 ppm of V. The relative standard deviation was found to be 0.84% (10 measurements were made, each containing 4 ppm V in 25 ml). In vanadium–HCPDMPTH–*p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde mixed-complex the ratio of vanadium to HCPDMPTH was determined by the mole-ratio⁴ and Job's method of continuous variation⁵. The ratio of vanadium to *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde was determined by curve-fitting method⁶, i.e. plots of log absorbance vs log[*p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde]. The results obtained show the formation of a 1:2:1 (metal–HCPDMPTH–*p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde) complex.

Effect of foreign ions: Chloride, bromide, nitrate and sulphate do not interfere. Urea,

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thiourea, triethanolamine, selenate, tellurates, alkali and alkaline earth metal ions and lanthanides do not interfere upto 2500 ppm. Interference due to Fe^{III} is eliminated by masking with trisodium phosphate (2 g). The tolerance limits for other ions (ppm, in parenthesis) are as follows: Cu^{II} (200); Mo^{VI} (1200); Zr^{IV} (120); W^{VI} (100); Ti^{IV} (250); Nb^{V} , Ta^{V} (250); Cd^{II} , Zn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Al^{III} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{II} (2200); phosphate, borate, phthalate (2500); oxalate, tartrate, citrate, arsenate (1500); chlorate, bromate, iodate, thiosulphate (1200).

Application of the method: The validity of the method was tested in two vanadium-tungsten steels and a tungsten-free low alloy steel. The results are shown in Table 1. The sample containing about 3 mg of vanadium was dissolved in 40% HNO_3 . Tungsten was removed before the determination of vanadium as hydrated oxide by filtration. The vanadium content of the filtrate was then determined as described above. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN STEEL SAMPLES

Sample	Certified V%	Found* V%	Standard deviation
Alloy steel (64a)	1.57	1.562	± 0.0084
High speed steel (241/1)	1.57	1.556	± 0.0078
Low alloy steel (25 2)	0.46	0.452	± 0.0092

* Average of six determinations.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium using *o*-Dianisidine as Reagent

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THE literature reports the formation of vanadium complexes with many organic reagents¹ and their extraction from aqueous solution into various organic solvents for analytical purposes². In this

paper a method is described for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium in alloy steels especially high speed steels by reaction with *o*-dianisidine. It has been observed that vanadium(V) reacts with *o*-dianisidine in acid medium forming a yellow-orange colour having λ_{max} at 440 nm, molar absorptivity $3.01 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandel sensitivity $0.00156 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.05–2 ppm of vanadium(V). The influence of various experimental factors such as reaction period, temperature, concentration of reagent and the influence of diverse ions has been studied. The method is simple and rapid. Instead of deleterious separation of Cr (which interferes) by extraction, the interference is avoided by dual wavelength measurement of absorbance and reference to a correction graph.

Experimental

A 0.05% solution of *o*-dianisidine in dilute sulphuric acid was made. Standard vanadium(V) solution was made by dissolving vanadium pentoxide (A.R., 1.786 g; equivalent to 1.0 g of V) in a minimum volume of 10% NaOH solution, neutralising the surplus alkali with HCl and diluting to 1 dm³ with distilled water to give the stock solution. A 100 ml portion of the solution was further diluted to 1 dm³ to give working solution containing 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of V^V.

Standard chromium(VI) solution containing 100 $\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$ of Cr was prepared from potassium dichromate (A.R.). Standard iron(II) solution was prepared by dissolving pure iron powder (1.0 g) in minimum quantity of HCl and diluting to 1 dm³ and was used for the background correction.

Acid mixture contained perchloric acid (sp. gr. 1.67; 1100 ml), phosphoric acid (sp. gr. 1.75; 300 ml) and water (100 ml).

Preparation of calibration graph: Aliquots of standard vanadium solution containing 10, 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 μg of vanadium(V) were mixed separately with iron(II) solution (10 ml) and acid mixture (15 ml) and fumed on a hot-plate until the volume was reduced to 5 ml. The solutions were then cooled, diluted to 25 ml, mixed with *o*-dianisidine reagent (4 ml), allowed to stand for 5 min at room temperature and diluted to 100 ml in a measuring flask. The absorbance of the yellow-orange solution was measured at 440 nm within 30 min. A plot of absorbance vs amount of V^V was linear.

Correction graph for chromium: The iron(II) solution (10 ml of 10 mg ml⁻¹) was mixed with each of the 0, 10, 30, 50 and 100 μg of chromium(VI) solution. The solutions were then fumed with the acid mixture (15 ml), then cooled and diluted to 25 ml and treated for colour development (as given in the procedure for vanadium) and the absorbance measured at 400 nm and 440 nm. A plot of absorbances at 400 nm against that at 440 nm was linear (Fig. 1). In unknown samples, a reference of

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